

EFFECT OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGY ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND INTEREST IN MOTOR VEHICLE MECHANIC WORKS IN GOVERNMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA

Victoria Bitrus Layopeh, Muhammad Muhammad Inti, Abubakar Sadiq Adamu

Department of Automobile Technology, Government Science and Technical College Amada Gombe State

Department of Mechanical Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi

vickylayopeh@gmail.com

07068217587

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID:

689C66B9D434A

Received: 2025-07-15

Published: 2025-08-16

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16885244>

44

Page No: 224-239

I. ABSTRACT

The study examined the Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Students Academic Achievement and interest in Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study had two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The design for the study was quasi-experimental that employed pre-test and post-test. The population of study was 222 students of seven technical colleges of Gombe State taking motor vehicle mechanic works trade. Two intact technical colleges were selected randomly and assigned to experimental and control groups. Data was collected using two instruments, firstly the Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Achievement Test (MVMWAT), which was adopted from NABTEB past questions. Consisting of 20 items. The second instrument used was Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Interest Inventory Questionnaire (MVMWIIQ) adapted from Eva. et al (2020). The instrument consists of 20 items measure with four-point rating scale, and was validated by three experts, Two from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi (ATBU) and one from Federal College of Education (Technical) Gombe. The reliability coefficient values of 0.80 for the MVMWAT and 0.87 for the MVMWIIQ were obtained using split-half and Cronbach's Alfa reliability methods respectively. The researcher and two trained research assistants (teachers) were involved during the data collection process. The study revealed among others, that students' that received instruction through cooperative learning strategy in motor vehicle mechanic works significantly obtained higher scores in their academic achievement and interest than the students that received instruction using convectional method of teaching. Based on these findings, the study recommended that technical college teachers particularly MVMW teachers should learn to use and integrate cooperative learning strategy in teaching their students. Finally, the study concluded that cooperative learning best enhanced students' achievement and interest in motor vehicle mechanic works at the Government Science and Technical Colleges level.

Key Words: Cooperative Learning Strategy, Academic Achievement, Motor Vehicle Mechanic works and Technical Colleges

Cite This Paper : Victoria Bitrus Layopeh, Muhammad Muhammad Inti and Abubakar Sadiq Adamu (2025). "EFFECT OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGY ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN MOTOR VEHICLE MECHANIC WORKS IN GOVERNMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)* ISSN 2249-9954, vol. 15, no.4, 2025, pp. 224-239. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16885244>

1. Introduction

Education is the most important tool to bring changes in the society by removing orthodoxy, superstitions and make people wise and rational (Basha, 2017). The curriculum designed for Technical College Education is comprehensive and broad-based, which aimed at broadening students' knowledge and Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works is one of the technical college education trades that is designed to develop the psycho-motor and physical qualities of students in technical colleges and thereby increasing their skills, knowledge, interest for self-improvement and national development (Basha, 2017). Also as asserted by Inuwa, Adamu and Isah (2023), many students of these days found it difficult to study Motor vehicle mechanics work (MVMW) because they see it as after graduation they will remain as mechanic or to teach any related MVMW subject without knowing that MVMW has many job opportunities that can lead them to become somebody in future. Inuwa *et al.* (2023), highlighted that, motor vehicle mechanics work trade (MVMW) is one of the subjects currently on the curriculum of the technical colleges.

Cooperative Learning strategy is the instructional use of small groups so that students work together to maximize their own and each other's learning (Mari & Gumel., 2015). Mari and Gumel continued that, in cooperative learning groups, students have two responsibilities; (i) to learn the assigned material and (ii) to well as making sure that all other members do likewise. They added that, simply placing students in groups and telling them to work together does not promote higher level of reasoning, interest and achievement.

Talan and Gulsecen (2019) have searched alternative strategies and teaching methods to enable students effectively participate in the teaching-learning process. These methods are

simulation methods, flipped method, brainstorming, scaffolding, expeditionary and above all is the use of Cooperative learning strategy which encourage active participation. The Cooperative learning strategy which is a new educational trend is regarded as one of these alternatives (Mendo-Lazaro, Barco, Rio, & Ramos, 2022). Cooperative learning strategy as stated by Molla and Muche (2018) involves students working together in small groups to accomplish shared goals. According to Johnson and Johnson (2019) cooperative learning is an instruction that involves students working in teams to accomplish a common goal. According to Inam Ur Rahim (2020), Cooperative Learning Strategy (CLS) combine and promote academic and social skills for universal educational goals. In order to be productive, cooperative learning groups must be structured to include the essential elements of positive interdependence (each member can succeed only and if all members succeed); face-to-face interaction; individual accountability (each member does his fair share and of work); interpersonal and small group skills; group processing (reflecting on how they work and improve). The effect of teaching methods on the students' achievements and interest is receiving a considerable attention from educators and researchers worldwide. What students learn is greatly influence by how they are taught (Inuwa, Adamu & Isah, 2023). It is important to note here that, academic achievement according to Jacobs cited in Nwodo (2015) depicts students' achievement on a measurement such as performance test, skill test, analytical thinking test etc.

Academic achievement is a result-oriented construct that encapsulates the extent of performance in a desired task (Rix, in Tran, 2014). In concord to this Barkley and Major (2020). noted that the type of material included in the teaching program is quite resistant to student interest. Evidence from literature showed that most teachers in Nigerian technical colleges predominantly use the conventional teaching method in teaching due to poor knowledge and none

exposure to other learner centred method leading to poor achievement and interest (Talan & Gulsecen., 2019). It is on this note that, the present study aimed in determining the effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on students' academic achievement and interest in Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work in Government Science and Technical colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. And that this study after publication in journals, textbooks and so on, this work will contribute immensely towards improving the achievement and interest of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Work trade students Government Science and in Technical Colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria and beyond.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the continuous efforts exerted by the Gombe State Ministry of Education, which aimed at improving the quality of the learning process, towards boosting teaching and learning of technical trades by employing trained technical colleges teachers, supply of textbooks, renovation of schools, appropriate training and re-training of teachers, scholarship to best graduating students and so on, but as asserted by Gombe State Ministry of Education (2024), record in regard to the achievement of the students in NABTEB Examination, MVMW results of 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 (Appendix II), was observed that the students in MVMW was very low, because the number of candidates who passed the examination in Gombe State seem to be dwindling year by year and it could be as a result of some factors like use of inappropriate teaching strategy, lack of student interest in the subject. Hence the need to be taught using appropriate method (s) because the conventional method namely teachers centered method employed by teachers in the teaching of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work trade at Government Science and Technical colleges have been found to have some defects and limitations.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to determine the effect of Cooperative Learning strategy on students' academic achievement and interest in Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research sought to:

- i. Determine the difference between the pre-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in the experimental and Control groups.
- ii. Find out the difference between the post-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in the experimental and Control groups.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the difference between the pre-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in both experimental and control groups?
- ii. What is the difference between the post-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in both experimental and control groups?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at 0.05 significant level;

H₀₁: There is no significance difference in the pre-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work students in the experimental and control groups.

H₀₂: There is no significance difference in the post-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work students in the experimental and control groups.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Cooperative Learning Strategy

Cooperative learning strategy is a pedagogical approach that involves students working together in small groups to achieve common learning goals (Johnson & Johnson, 2019). Johnson

and Johnson, cooperative learning has been shown to be beneficial for students across a wide racial, ethnic, socioeconomic and disability spectrum, as well as those from differing academic skill levels. According to Alghamdi (2018) teachers who uses cooperative learning approach assign students to heterogeneous groups to complete instructional activities. As stated by Alghamdi, successful cooperative learning programs focus on: teacher-provided direct instruction on pro-social methods of communication: (1) Social skills decision-making, and conflict resolution; assignment of roles that involve students in the learning process while; (2) Positive interdependence allowing for division of responsibility (e.g., student note-taker, time-keeper, results-reporter, etc.); embedded individual accountability assessments that make each; (3) Individual student accountability student responsible for contributing to the group assignment effort; provision of adequate class time for students to discuss the assignment, share; (4) One-on-one interaction ideas, assist each other, and develop ideas; provision skill instruction to allow students to determine their own progress; (5) Group processing towards achievement of the group goal(s).

In the same vein, Aliyu, (2024). cooperative learning strategy is an instructional method in which students work in small groups to accomplish a common learning goal with the guidance of the teacher. He added that, cooperative learning strategy is a strategy that involves group work and encourages students' interest in learning. cooperative learning strategy helps students feel like an integral and necessary part of achieving the teacher's objectives and it promotes greater responsibility towards learning and others. This includes understanding the strategy, applying appropriate techniques and adopting suitable roles for both the teacher and the student. According to Ogunbote, & Dawodu, (2023).

2.2 Concept of Academic achievement

Academic achievement of students is an important factor affecting the achievement of higher educational goals (Zhu, 2016). Academic achievement is a direct manifestation of learning effectiveness and a valid indicator to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and education in higher education as well as the overall development of students. According to Jury, Burno, and Darmon (2018) academic achievement of technical college students is influenced by various factors, and researchers have done a lot of research. Jury et al. added that, the analysis of academic achievement has gradually become the focus of research by scholars and experts, but the definition of the concept is still controversial. Similarly, Fan and Williams (2018) stated that, academic achievement is used as an outcome variable to investigate how to motivate technical college students to learn while promoting their interest towards learning.

Academic is explained as academic work, school work (Jury, Bruno & Darmon, 2018) lamented that, academic achievement is considered to be equal to academic performance, and the common measure of academic achievement of college students is GPA (credit point average), which can be accurately calculated from the marks of each course to measure students' academic achievement. To Jury et al., academic means the result of school work. For example, test scores. On his own part, Lamas (2015) stated that, the term academic achievement refers to the results achieved by students as a result of the accumulation of learning. To Lamas, achievement refers to the completion and attainment of a certain level that a student can achieve after a series of education or training, while performance refers to the result of an examination in a subject or a whole course.

2.3 Concept of Technical Education

Technical-education is defined as that aspect of education which leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. (Udoudo, & Udoetuk, 2020). Technical Education is used as a comprehensive term in the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life (Zirkle & Jeffery, 2017). Adeyemi, (2023). defines technical education as a form of education whose primary purpose is to prepare persons for employment in recognized occupation. As asserted also by Okolie, Nwajiuba, Binuomote, Ehiobuche, Igu, & Ajoke, (2021) technical education provides its learners to be an industrialist in a particular field, which could help in the country's economic growth. Technical education has played lots of important roles in the country such as provision of employment opportunities for the youths of the country, improvement of living standards, skills acquired has helps the individual and also the nation to boost in all sectors, promoting of political stability it also helps in employment opportunities in the country and a drastic reduction in crime rate.

2.4 Overview of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work Trade

Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works (MVMW) is one of the trades offered in the Science and Technical Colleges in Nigeria. According to Saue (2020), MVMW trade offers procedural skills leading to the production of craftsmen/women, technicians, and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant. Motor vehicle mechanic work is a fundamental component of technical education, especially within the context of Automobile Engineering programs in Nigeria (Medugu, Udin, & Saman, 2014). Improving the skills of motor vehicle mechanics, particularly in the utilization of digital diagnostic tools, is crucial for ensuring efficient maintenance and repair

services (Opeyemi & Benjamin, 2020). The performance of the motor vehicle industry is influenced by factors such as policy liberalization and market trends (Bopage & Sharma, 2014).

The curriculum of the MVMW programme is broadly divided into three components: namely; General Education, Trade Theory, and Supervised Industrial Training/Work Experience (Brincks, Domanski, Klier, and Rubenstein, (2018).). Brincks *et al.* (2018) added that, while the general education component of the curriculum aims at providing the students with complete secondary education in critical subjects like English Language, Economics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Entrepreneurial Studies, and Mathematics, the trade theory component exposes students to operational principles of various automobile systems and the technical know-how for their maintenance. Similarly, Okwelle, Yoedu, and Ajie, (2017). stated that, industrial training/work experience provides students with opportunity of coming face-to-face with reality of the world of works. Okwelle et al, (2017) continued that, in order to translate the core aim of the MVMW trade into reality, teaching and learning becomes the sole pathway to acquisition of knowledge, skills, and attitude. On their own perspectives, Saue and Yekorogha (2023) stated that, Motor Vehicle Mechanic (MVM) trade is one of the vocational training skill programmes operated basically through the informal setting with apprenticeship mode of instruction.

3. Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, specifically, a pretest-posttest nonequivalent control group design. The population consists 222 NTC II students enrolled in Motor Vehicle Mechanic works during the 2023/2024 academic session. A Random sampling technique was used to select two schools from the seven Technical Colleges offering Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Trade in Gombe State. The sample for the study consisted of 44 students from the two intact classes, 25 students from school A which served as the experimental group and 19 students from school B which also served as the control group, members of the experimental group were taught using cooperative learning strategy while the control group were taught using

the conventional teaching method. The instrument for data collection was Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Achievement Test (MVMWAT) which was adopted from NABTEB past examination questions (2020-2023) and the Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works interest inventory questionnaire (MVMWII) which was adapted from Evan et al, (2020). Data collection was facilitated by two research assistants (motor vehicle mechanic works teachers) who administered the test to the NTCII motor vehicle mechanic works students in the selected technical colleges. Mean, standard deviation and t-tests (independent and paired samples t-test was employed the independent sample t-test was used to compare the mean scores of experimental and control groups

4. Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Pre-test Mean Achievement Scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Students in Both Control and Experimental Groups.

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Diff
Pre-test	Experimental	25	24.28	3.518	0.09
	Control	19	24.37	4.153	
Total		44			

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviation.

The output of descriptive statistic presented in Table 1 showed the results of pre-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in both control and experimental groups. The results, indicated that there was a slight difference in the mean achievement of experimental group (M = 24.28, Std. Dev = 3.518) and control group (M = 24.37, Std. Dev = 4.153) at the pretest stage. This indicated that, the students of experimental and control group are equal in their Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works achievement prior to the experiment.

Table 2: Independent Samples t-test of Pre-test Mean Achievement Scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Groups	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances					Decision
		N	Mean	Std. Dev	t-value	p-value	
Pre-test	Experimental	25	24.28	3.518	-.076	.937	Accepted
	Control	19	24.37	4.153			

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviation.

The outcome of independent-samples t-test in Table 2 indicated that there was no significant difference between pre-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work students in the experimental ($M = 24.28$, $Std. Dev = 3.518$), and control groups ($M = 24.37$, $Std. Dev = 4.153$), $t(42) = -0.076$, $p = .939$. Null hypothesis one was therefore, accepted. This finding suggested that the students of cooperative learning strategy and conventional method come from the same population because, at the start of the experiment, they are equal statistically in terms of their Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work achievements scores.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Post-Test Mean Achievement Scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Students in Both Control and Experimental Groups.

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Diff
Post-test	Experimental	25	70.64	5.507	
	Control	19	49.53	4.551	21.11
	Total	44			

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviations

A descriptive statistic was performed to find out the difference between the post-test mean achievement scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works students in both control and experimental groups. The result in Table 3, revealed that there was a difference in the post-test mean achievement scores of NTC II students taught Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works using Cooperative Learning strategy ($M = 70.64$, $Std. Dev = 5.507$) and those taught using conventional method ($M = 49.53$, $Std. Dev = 4.551$). This indicated that, technical colleges Students taught Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Trade using Cooperative Learning strategy have a better performance compared to their counterparts taught using conventional method.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test of Post-test Mean Achievement Scores of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances							
Variable	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	t-value	p-value	Decision
Post-test	Experimental	25	70.64	5.507	13.552	.000	Rejected
	Control	19	49.53	4.551			

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviation.

The statistical evidence of independent-samples t-test presented in Table4 indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in the post-test mean achievement scores of Technical Colleges students taught Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work using cooperative learning strategy ($M = 70.64$, Std. Dev = 5.507) and those taught using conventional method ($M = 49.53$, Std. Dev = 4.551), $t(42) = 13.552$, $p = .000$. which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Null hypothesis two was therefore, rejected. This finding suggested that cooperative learning strategy had a significant effect on students' academic achievement and interest in motor vehicle mechanic works in technical colleges.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Pre-test and Post-test Mean Achievement Scores of Cooperative Learning Strategy

Group	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Diff
Cooperative Learning strategy	Pretest	25	24.28	3.518	
	Post-test	25	70.64	5.507	46.36

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviation.

The statistical evidence presented in Table 5 shows the pre-test and post-test mean achievement scores of students taught Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works using the Cooperative Learning strategy at Technical Colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. The post-test mean score ($M= 70.64$, Std. Dev = 5.507) is higher than the pre-test mean score ($M = 24.28$, Std. Dev = 3.518). This result indicates that Cooperative Learning strategy improved the students' achievement in Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works of Technical Colleges students in Gombe State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Paired Samples t-test of Pre-test and Post-test Mean Achievement Scores of Cooperative Learning Strategy Students

Group	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)
cooperative learning strategy	Pretest	25	24.28	3.158	20.604	.000
	Post-test	25	70.64	5.507		

Note: N=Number of students, Std. Dev= Standard deviation.

A paired samples t-test was conducted to find out the differences in mean achievement scores between the pre-test and post-test for students taught Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work using the cooperative learning strategy at Technical Colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. The results, shown in Table 6, indicate a statistically significant difference between the pre-test scores ($M = 24.28$, Std. Dev = 3.518) and post-test scores of students in cooperative learning strategy ($M = 70.64$, Std. Dev = 5.507), $t(24) = 20.604$, $p = .000$. Consequently, Null Hypothesis 3 was rejected. This suggests that the cooperative learning strategy significantly improved students' achievement in Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work at these technical colleges.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of research question one and its corresponding hypothesis showed that statistically there was no existence of statistically significant difference between pre-test motor vehicle mechanic works achievement of cooperative learning strategy and conventional method students at the pretest. The finding is consistent with Okeke and Alichu (2022) who conducted a study on the effect of cooperative learning of secondary school students' achievement and interest that there was equality in the achievement of students who were assigned to the experimental and those who were assigned to the conventional teaching approach before exposure to the treatment. The finding is also in line with the studies of Obasi (2022); Okwell *et al.*, (2017). The studies observed non-existence of significant difference in achievement score of experimental and control group students at the pretest stage.

The findings of research question two which was supported by test of its corresponding hypothesis revealed that cooperative learning had a significant effect on students' academic achievement and interest at technical colleges in Gombe State. This finding aligns with study of Ihejiamaizu and Agiande (2020) who conducted a study on Effect of cooperative learning strategy on students' academic performance in secondary school Biology, the findings indicated a statistically significant difference in academic performance between the two groups. This suggests that students taught using cooperative learning strategy had a higher academic performance gain score than those taught using conventional method. The result revealed that cooperative learning had a positive impact on students' performance. The finding also concurred with Inam-Ur-Raihim (2020) who investigated the effectiveness of cooperative teaching learning in mathematics had a

positive effect on secondary school students' academic achievement compared to the traditional method.

Research question three and its corresponding hypothesis three revealed that there was a statistically significant difference between the pre-test mean scores and post-test scores of students in the Experimental Group in favour of post-test scores. The finding concurred with the study of Ajaja and Mezieobi (2018) found that cooperative learning positively impacted student performance in social studies, the result showed that students performed highly using cooperative learning instructional strategy irrespective of their ability level. This suggests that using cooperative learning strategy is beneficial on students' performance and also improves their social interaction skills and foster meta-cognition. The finding is also consistent with the study of Tyav and Onyilo (2017) that investigated the effect of simulation on motor vehicle mechanic works students' achievement and retention. The findings revealed that students taught with simulation achieved higher achievement in both post-test and retention than those taught with the conventional method. This suggests that the benefits of simulation had a higher achievement and retention.

Conclusion

This study focused on the effect of the cooperative learning strategy on students' academic achievement in Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work in Technical colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that cooperative learning strategy significantly enhances students' academic achievement in Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work compared to conventional teaching method in technical colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. The findings stress the impact of cooperative learning as an instructional strategy for technical education, which can support students' skill development and sustained interest in technical subjects like Motor Vehicle Mechanics. Educators and policymakers in technical education should consider incorporating cooperative learning approaches to improve educational outcomes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings obtained in this study:

- i. Technical colleges in Gombe State should integrate cooperative learning strategies into the curriculum for Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work and other technical subjects.

- ii. Regular professional development programs should be organized for teachers of Motor Vehicle Mechanics Work, focusing on cooperative learning techniques and methods for their effective application in technical classrooms.
- iii. Education policymakers should ensure technical colleges have access to necessary resources, such as toolkits and instructional materials for cooperative learning in technical education.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, O. A. (2023). Vocational Technical Education as a tool for sustainable development in Nigeria. *Engineering Research Journal*, **3**(5), 13-26.
- Alghamdi, R. (2018). Efl learners' behaviour states during cooperative learning strategy. *International Journal of Linguistics*, **10**(6), 64. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijl.v10i6.14006>
- Aliyu, A. (2024). Effect of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. Cross River State, Nigeria (June 22, 2024).
- Barkley, E. F., & Major, C. H. (2020). Student engagement techniques: A handbook for college faculty. John Wiley & Sons.
- Basha, C. (2017). Role of education in social change. *International Journal of Advanced Educational Research*, **2**(5), 236-240.
- Bopage, L. & Sharma, K. (2014). An analysis of trade performance of the Australian passenger motor vehicle industry: trends, patterns, and determinants. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Business*, **15**(3), 197-210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10599231.2014.934624>
- Brincks, C., Domanski, B., Klier, T., & Rubenstein, J. (2018). Integrated peripheral markets in the auto industries of Europe and North America. *International Journal of Automotive Technology and Management*, **18**(1), 1.
- Fan, W., & Williams, C. (2018, July). The mediating role of student motivation in the linking of perceived school climate and achievement in reading and mathematics. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 3, p. 50). Frontiers Media SA.
- Gombe State Ministry of Education Exam record Unit (Gombe state government 2024)
- Inam Ur Rahim, S.P. (2020). Effect of cooperative learning strategies on academic achievement in mathematics. *International Journal of Reflective Research in Social Sciences*, **3**(1), 63-66

- Inuwa, I. M., Adamu, S. B. & Isah, M. K. (2023). Effect of Dreyful Model on Motor Vehicle Mechanic Work Trade (MVMW) on Students Performance and Interest in Colleges, in Bauchi State. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education Research*, **9**(1);1-8.
- Johnson, D. & Johnson, R. (2019). Cooperative learning: the foundation for active learning. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.81086>
- Jury, M., Bruno. A. and Darmon, C. (2018). Doing better (or worse) than one's parents: Social status, mobility, and performance- avoidance goals. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, **88**(4), 659-674.
- Lamas, H. A. (2015). School Performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology-Propositos y Representaciones*, **3**(1), 351-385.
- Mari, J. & Gumel, S. (2015). Effects of jigsaw model of cooperative learning on self-efficacy and achievement in chemistry among concrete and formal reasoners in colleges of education in nigeria. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, **5**(3), 196-199.
- Mendo-Lazaro, S., Barco, B., Rio, M., & Ramos, V. (2022). The impact of cooperative learning on university students' academic goals. *Frontiers in Psychology*, **12**. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.787210>.
- Medugu, V., Udin, A., & Saman, M. (2014). Medium of instruction (I1 versus I2): which is in automobile engineering? *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, **32**, 81-86. <https://doi.org/10.18052/www.scipress.com/ilshs.32.81>
- Molla, E. & Muche, M. (2018). Impact of cooperative learning approaches on students' academic achievement and laboratory proficiency in biology subject in selected rural schools, ethiopia. *Education Research International*, 1-9.
- Ogunbote, S., & Dawodu, R. A. (2023). Co-operative learning method and metalwork student's academic achievement in technical colleges. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, **39**(4), 1514-1519.,
- Okwelle, P., Yoedu, T. B. & Ajie, M. P. (2017). Technical Skills Needed by Motor Vehicle Mechanic Apprentice to Establish Standard Motor Mechanic Enterprise in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Scientific & Engineering Technologies Research*. **5**. 27-34.
- Okolie, U. C., Elom, E. N., Igwe, P. A., Binuomote, M. O., Nwajiuba, C. A., & Igu, N. C. (2021). Improving graduate outcomes: Implementation of problem-based learning in TVET systems of Nigerian higher education. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, **11**(1), 92-110.
- Opeyemi, O. & Benjamin, U. (2020). Strategies for enhancing roadside motor vehicle mechanics on basic computer skills for effective manipulation of automotive digital diagnostic tools

- in nsukka urban of enugu state. *American Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering*, **5**(6), 71.
- Saue, B & Yekorogha, L. (2023). Impact of Motor Vehicle Mechanics' Work Skills on Sustainable Development of Graduates in Rivers State.
- Talan, T., & Gulsecen, S. (2019). The effect of a flipped classroom on students' achievements, academic engagement and satisfaction levels. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, **20**(4), 31-60.
- Udoudo, N. J., & Udoetuk, U. S. (2020). Enhancing Vocational Skills Acquisition among Technical Education Students in Tertiary Institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Realities, JERA*, **10**(1), 1-12..
- Zhu, S. (2016). A review of college students' academic achievement research. *Teaching and education (Higher Education Forum)* (27), 36-38.
- Zirkle, C. J., & Jeffery, J. O. (2017). Career and technical education administration: Requirements, certification/licensure, and preparation. *Career and Technical Education Research*, **42**(1), 21-33.